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Abstract. *If we look at Khurshid Dostmuhammad's works, we can see his unique style, which is reflected in this article.*

Keywords: "Market", "Interrogation", unconventionality, hero mentality.

ПРОЗАИЧЕСКОЕ ИСКУССТВО ХУРШИДА ДОСТМУХАММАДА

Аннотация. *Если мы посмотрим на творчество Хуршида Достмухаммада, то увидим его неповторимый стиль, который нашел отражение в этой статье.*

Ключевые слова: «Рынок», «Допрос», нестандартность, менталитет героя.

INTRODUCTION

Journalist and writer Khurshid Dostmuhammad was born in 1951 in Tashkent. After graduating from high school, in 1969-1973 he studied at the Faculty of Journalism of Tashkent State University. He worked in the "Fan" publishing house, "Fan and Life" magazine, and "Kishloq Haqiqatii" newspaper. Since 1986, he has been working as a department head, deputy editor-in-chief, and editor-in-chief in "Yosh Kuch" magazine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

He was the editor-in-chief of the independent newspaper "Hurriyat", published for the first time in the republic, co-chairman of the socio-political fund for the democratization and support of mass media of Uzbekistan, and worked as the editor-in-chief of the magazine "Uzbekiston pryssi". Currently, the Oliy Majlis of the Republic operates in the Legislative Chamber. He is also noted for his articles as a literary critic, candidate of philological sciences. Khurshid Dostmuhammad translated into Uzbek the story of the Japanese writer Akutagawa Ryunoske's "Rasyomon's Gate" and Temur Polatov's novel "Seven Joys and Forty Sorrows".

RESULTS

The writer's first story was published in "Guliston" magazine in 1981, and his first short story "Nigoh" was published in 1987 in "Yoshlik" magazine. The first book "The house at the foot of the yard" was published in 1989. Since then, his stories "Panoh", "Oromkursi", "Interrogation", "Pure Uzbek murder", "Hijranim mingdir mening", the novel "Bazar" and dozens of stories have been published. Among several short stories from the book "Jajman" (1995) of the author, there are also stories such as "Mahzuna", "Jajman", "Ibn Mughanni", "I am alone - you", "House in the eyeball". Adib was awarded the "Ofarin" award in 2000 for the novel "Bazar", "Hijranim mingdir mening" and "The joys of free suffering".

The television feature film "Chayongul" (2000), created as the author of the script, was warmly received by a wide audience. The stories "The Road to the Quiet House", "The Copywriter's Heir", "The Curse of the Innocent Bird" and "The Silent Man" opened a new page in the writer's work in the following years.

DISCUSSION

Like other works of Khurshid Dostmuhammad, the novel "Bozor" has an important place in Uzbek literature. In it, various characters and dissimilar destinies are detailed. "Market" is a novel that makes people think deeply and tries to interpret human life in terms of the market. The main character of the work, Fozilbek, is a young man who worked in seven pink markets,

and whose father was also a market leader. A young man who has to live with his brothers, father and stepmother does not work anywhere, he does not come from the market. When asked about his profession, he answers that he works as a janitor at the "Shuur" company. He was the youngest in the family, and his mother gave birth to him and left this bright world. Thirsty for this love, he grows up to be HARD, he wanders the market looking for wisdom everywhere, immersed in his thoughts. Khurshid Dostmuhammad's novel "Oyin" consists of several chapters. In this novel, together with the events of children's childhood, it is also mentioned about the games that the children of the Uzbek people played when they were young, that is, what kind of games they were engaged in are embodied in this work. . In the novel, such characters as Fazliddin, Mirahmad, Baqo, Lutfulla, Yahya participate in the development of the main events. In the short story "Nighoh" we see an unconventional style, as in other works of Khurshid Dostmuhammad. Because this story does not follow the same pattern as the stories of other writers, while the events are happening, the psyche of the hero is described among them, and the surrounding events also have their influence on the subject of the work.

CONCLUSIONS

The story describes the bek driving a tram. In this process, the events of the work go to the other side, that is, the flying insects are described. The image of nature is also reflected in the imagination of the hero. Even in such places, it shows the writer's unique style. Another one of the writer's short stories is "Interrogation". In this story, Bozorboy and Shabnam's family worries, Bozorboy's tractor business, village people's lifestyle and mainly Bozorboy's problems are described. The following sentences were taken as an epigraph to the story: "Before being questioned, question yourselves." Through these sentences taken from the hadith, the essence of the story and its content are explained

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